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The Necessity of Improving the Mechanism of Management of Tourist Services in the Republic of Uzbekistan

Tukhtarova Feruzakhon Yuldashevna

«University of Economics and Pedagogy», Uzbekistan

***Annotation:** This article discusses the need to improve the mechanism of management of tourist services in the Republic of Uzbekistan.*

***Key words:** tourism, tourism industry, management, mechanism, infrastructure, problems, digitalization, development strategy.*

The economic structure of almost all countries of the world has undergone profound changes in recent decades. A global trend has become the movement of resources from the sphere of material production to the service sector, which ensures satisfaction of the needs of the population in various services and largely determines the way of life of people.

Tourism is an integral part of the lifestyle of modern society - one of the sectors of the classification of services that can be the subject of international trade (World Trade Organization) is "tourism services and travel-related services". Since the beginning of the 21st century, international tourism has accounted for about 30% of world trade in services, and it has provided the highest export revenues.

The main and stable trend of the pre-crisis development of the travel industry was a continuous increase in tourist arrivals: about 25 million tourists in 1950, 300 million in 1980, 650 million in 2000, and one and a half billion people in 2019. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, the tourist flow sharply decreased to 400 million people, but in 2021 the recovery of the industry (450 million people) begins, which continued in 2022 (according to UNWTO estimates, there were 700 million tourists in the world from January to September). It is expected that in 2024, global tourism indicators will return to the level of 2019.

The sharply increased demand for holidays in Uzbekistan, including due to state support, leads to the improvement of the mechanism of the tourism business in the context of digitalization, the theoretical understanding and practical assessments of which are of significant scientific interest.

Uzbekistan has consistently implemented comprehensive measures to develop tourism as one of the strategic sectors of the national economy, ensuring its diversification and accelerated development of regions, creating new jobs, increasing incomes and quality of life of the population, as well as improving investment attractiveness.

The liberalization of the visa regime, simplification of the procedure for registration of foreign citizens, and the provision of benefits and preferences for the development of the tourism industry have created favorable conditions for the effective promotion of national tourism potential both in domestic and foreign markets.

At the same time, the analysis shows the imperfection of the regulatory framework governing the tourism industry, the lack of rules for the provision of certain types of tourist services and visa regimes widely used in world practice, differentiated by category of foreign citizens, terms and purposes of their stay.

The accelerated development of tourism is also hampered by the lack of accommodation facilities and infrastructure facilities, especially during the tourist season, insufficient coordination of the passenger transportation system by various modes of transport, as well as low organization of information support for tourists about the existing tourist potential, inefficiency of marketing campaigns to promote domestic tourism, features of cultural heritage sites and pilgrimages in the regions of the country. In order to ensure the sustainable growth of the tourism industry in Uzbekistan and bring it to the level of international standards, it is necessary to solve a number of complex tasks that will help eliminate existing barriers and create conditions for the effective functioning of tourism as an important part of the national economy.

Firstly, the most important problem remains the modernization and development of infrastructure, including the construction of new accommodation facilities (hotels, guest houses, resort complexes), improving the quality of service and increasing the competitiveness of existing facilities. It is important to create an infrastructure that meets international standards and introduce innovative approaches, for example, the development of environmentally friendly and sustainable tourism services, which will help attract tourists interested in an environmentally oriented vacation.

Secondly, it is necessary to optimize the transport system that ensures the accessibility of tourist regions. In Uzbekistan, a significant part of the tourist flow is directed to such historical and cultural centers as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva and Tashkent. However, the development of transport accessibility in these regions remains an important problem, especially during the peak tourist season. The development of air services, improving the quality of roads, creating convenient transport routes, as well as the integration of various modes of transport (trains, buses, domestic flights) will help to increase the level of convenience and reduce the cost of traveling around the country.

In addition, it is worth noting that information support and marketing play a key role in promoting the tourism potential of Uzbekistan. At the moment, a significant part of tourists rely on online platforms and applications to plan their trips, search for information about places and cultural sites. Uzbekistan needs to strengthen its digital strategy by creating high-quality and informative online resources, mobile applications, as well as promote the country at international tourism exhibitions and on social networks in order to strengthen its position as an attractive destination for tourists.

Special attention should be paid to the training of personnel in the field of tourism. Qualified specialists who will be able to work effectively with international tourists, provide a high level of service and awareness, are the key to the successful development of the tourism industry. It is

important to introduce training programs for specialists focused on sustainable and environmentally friendly tourism development, as well as the introduction of new digital technologies into the industry.

Thirdly, it is extremely important to improve the regulatory framework governing tourism activities. This includes both the development of legislative initiatives and the creation of clear standards of service quality, the creation of new types of tourist services such as agrotourism, gastronomic tourism, medical tourism and others. Differentiation of visa regimes for different categories of foreign citizens, simplification of obtaining visas, as well as improvement of procedures for registration and control of foreign citizens are important steps towards creating an attractive climate for international tourism.

An important aspect is to improve cooperation with private and public investment structures to attract investment in the tourism industry, which will ensure an increase in the number of modern infrastructure facilities, improve the quality of services and affordable prices. It also helps to create new jobs and stimulate local businesses.

In the long term, tourism development in Uzbekistan could play an important role in both economic growth and strengthening cultural ties, as well as promoting the country's unique heritage. Given its rich history and cultural heritage, Uzbekistan has a chance to become a major tourist destination in Central Asia, attracting visitors from all over the world.

However, to achieve this goal, it is essential to continue working on infrastructure improvement, service enhancement, digitalization of the industry, and implementation of innovative approaches in tourism development.

Examples from world practice and recent experience demonstrate the significance of implementing these strategies and objectives.

Modernization of Infrastructure

In recent decades, Turkey has seen significant development in its tourism infrastructure, particularly in regions such as Antalya and Istanbul. This is due to the significant investments made in the construction of modern hotels and resorts, including environmentally friendly projects. These initiatives have allowed Turkey to become a leading destination for foreign tourists.

Similar projects could be implemented in Uzbekistan, such as creating ecotourism complexes in natural areas and developing historical centers. These efforts would help to increase the country's attractiveness to tourists and contribute to its economic growth.

Optimization of the transportation system in the UAE has led to the establishment of an efficient network connecting tourist destinations with major airports and other parts of the country. This has been achieved through the development of air services and the construction of high-speed railway lines, similar to those seen in China. These initiatives have significantly increased tourist traffic.

In Uzbekistan, efforts to improve transportation infrastructure, such as expanding air connections and modernizing railway systems, can enhance the overall travel experience within the country. These developments can attract tourists who are interested in exploring not only major cities but also remote locations like the Kyzyl Kum desert and the mountainous areas of Ferghana.

Information support and marketing: Spain actively uses digital technologies to promote tourism, creating high-quality online resources and mobile applications for tourists. It also actively participates in international tourism exhibitions. Uzbekistan could take a similar approach, creating innovative mobile apps for tourists that would help them not only plan their routes but also learn about cultural events, historical sites, and natural attractions in the country.

Personnel training: Thailand and Vietnam have developed programs for training tourism professionals, including courses on ecotourism and sustainable development. This is an important aspect in maintaining a high standard of service and complying with environmental standards. Uzbekistan could introduce similar programs in universities and specialized institutions, training professionals who can work within the tourism industry and maintain international service standards.

Regulatory framework and visa regimes: Visa policy in Georgia has been liberalized, which has led to a significant increase in the number of foreign tourists. Based on international experience, Uzbekistan should improve its visa policy to create more flexible conditions for different categories of tourists and simplify the process of obtaining visas.

Attracting investment in the tourism industry: The government of Egypt actively attracts private investment in tourism infrastructure, such as new hotel complexes and renovated archaeological sites. This has led to an increase in tourist numbers. In Uzbekistan, investments can be directed towards developing new tourist facilities like specialized resorts for eco-tourism, agro-tourism, medical tourism, and gastronomic tours.

Each of these examples demonstrates the significance of a strategic approach to the development of the tourism industry, which can be a crucial factor in the economic growth of Uzbekistan.

List of used literature:

1. Всемирная торговая организация. (2019). Туризм и международная торговля услугами. [Электронный ресурс]. Доступно на: <https://www.wto.org>
2. Бондаренко, В. В. & Тарасенко, И. Ю. (2021). Туризм как сектор экономики: мировые тенденции и роль в национальной экономике. *Экономика и социология*, 5(2), 112-124.
3. Госкомстат Республики Узбекистан. (2022). Основные показатели туристической отрасли Республики Узбекистан. Ташкент: Госкомстат.
4. Мангулова, Н. А. & Черкасов, Ю. А. (2020). Экономика туризма: теоретические и практические аспекты. Ташкент: ИСЭП.
5. Проблемы и перспективы развития туризма в Узбекистане. (2021). *Журнал туризма и отдыха*. Ташкент: АТУ.
6. Юнусова, М. Х. (2021). Развитие туристической инфраструктуры в Узбекистане: проблемы и решения. Ташкент: Экономика и финансы.
7. Всемирная организация туризма (UNWTO). (2022). Туризм в мире: статистика и прогнозы. [Электронный ресурс]. Доступно на: <https://www.unwto.org>
8. Н.Т. Сафина, Ш. Худойбердиева. Совершенствование процесса принятия управленческих решений в организации. *Formation of psychology and pedagogy as interdisciplinary sciences*. 2024/5/13 <https://interoncof.com/index.php/italy/issue/view/18>
9. Khalilov N. Kh. Foreign experience on the implementation of a quality management system. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*. Vol. 48 (2024): 13/06/2024. https://gospodarkainnowacje-pl.openconference.us/index.php/issue_view_32/article/view/2748
10. Международный банк реконструкции и развития (IBRD). (2022). Инвестиции в туристическую инфраструктуру: мировой опыт и применения для Узбекистана. [Электронный ресурс]. Доступно на: <https://www.worldbank.org>

11. Рябова, О. В. (2020). Развитие экотуризма как направления устойчивого туризма в Центральной Азии. Алматы: Издательство КазНУ.
12. Асатуллаев, М. А. (2019). Устойчивое развитие туризма в Узбекистане: вызовы и перспективы. Ташкент: Академия государственного и общественного строительства